

Phlomis anisodonta Rech.f.: Analysis of Distribution Area and Morphological Differential Characters

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Abstract. This article discusses the origin of *Phlomis anisodonta*, a species belonging to the *Phlomis* genus within the Lamiaceae family, *Phlomis anisodonta* highlighting its distinct morphological characteristics that set it apart from other species, as well as its unique medicinal properties. Based on data presented in herbarium specimens, the article also outlines the dynamics of the species over the years.

Keywords. *Phlomis*, *Phlomis anisodonta*

INTRODUCTION. *Phlomis* L. is one of the largest genera of the Lamiaceae family. *Phlomis* is widely distributed from East China through Eurasia and the Mediterranean to Portugal and Morocco (Figure 1). C. Moench recognizes many morphological characters of species belonging to the *Phlomis* genus and considers them to have sufficient morphological differences to be divided into *Phlomis* L. and *Phlomoides* Moench [1]. In recent years, a number of modern studies have been conducted on the *Phlomis* genus in Iran. The genus is among the morphologically poorly studied taxa and requires new approaches to conducting field studies and molecular analyses of its taxonomy, geography, morphology [5].

Plants belonging to the genus *Phlomis* are characterized by their high degree of evolutionary adaptation to various climatic conditions, as well as their rich pharmacological potential. *Phlomis anisodonta* Rech.f. is one of the least studied, but morphologically unique representatives of this genus. This article provides a scientific analysis of this species based on its geographical distribution, ecological adaptations, and diagnostic morphological characters.

The genus *Phlomis* has more than 100 species, depending on its distribution area [3]. The international database Plants of the World Online includes 93 species, the list of Central Asian flora includes 17 species [4], and the flora of Uzbekistan includes 12 species [8, 9].

Phlomis olgae, a member of the genus *Phlomis*, is distinguished by its unique characteristics. The complete chemical properties of this species are very limited compared to other members of the genus, and it is one of the most widely distributed species in Iran.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY.

The identification of the species was carried out based on information from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF, <https://www.gbif.org/>), the Moscow Virtual Herbarium (<https://plant.depo.msu.ru>), and the <https://www.plantarium.ru> platform.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Phlomis anisodonta is found mainly in the West Asian region, in Iran, Afghanistan and partly in Central Asia (especially the southern mountainous regions of Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan). Geobotanically, this area corresponds to the Iran-Deccan mountain systems, the Khorasan ranges and the Pamir-Olay floristic regions [12].

The plant usually grows in xeromorphic, semi-desert or subalpine zones at an altitude of 1500–3000 m, on stony-rocky substrates, dry brunizm or calcareous soils. Climatic conditions are continental, with dry and hot summers and relatively cold winters[13].

Figures 1 and 2. Morphological structure and distribution of the genus *Phlomis anisodonta*

Morphological and diagnostic signs; Life form: *Phlomis anisodonta* develops as a perennial herb or low semi-shrub. According to the system of life forms, it belongs to the hemicryptophyte or xerophyte group. Stem: 30–100 cm tall, erect, the surface epidermis is densely covered with hairs (trichomatose).

Leaves are opposite, simple, oblong or lanceolate. The leaf margins are serrated, sometimes asymmetrically serrated — this is reflected in the name of the species (*anisodonta* — “variously serrated”)[12].

Flowers are located in verticillata inflorescences, yellowish, rarely greenish-yellow. The corolla has a two-lipped structure: the upper lip is thyroid-shaped, the lower lip is three-lobed, the central one is wider and directed forward.

Calyx (floret) is tubular, with 5 teeth, covered with dense hairs, which serve as a protection against dust and moisture. Androecium - 4 stamens, didynamically located; gynoecium - a two-celled ovary, located above.

Fruit: Consists of 4 nuts, each nut is egg-shaped, smooth on the surface, each filled with a seed[13].

CONCLUSION. *Phlomis anisodonta* is a species with unique morphological and ecological characteristics, with a narrow distribution and possible signs of endemism. Its morphological differential characters (especially the asymmetry in leaf teeth, the degree of hairiness, and the structure of the flower inflorescence) can be used as the main taxonomic criteria for distinguishing it from other closely related species. In the framework of future scientific research, it is of great scientific importance to study the phytochemical and genetic characteristics of this species.

The plant differs from other species in terms of its chemical composition, its medicinal properties are very high, it contains flavonoids, proteins, glycosides and a number of other substances, which are also included in many of our current medicines. *Phlomis olgae* is also useful in preventing erosion on mountain slopes.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

Widespread planting of *Phlomis* and other species included in its composition allows for high results in medicine.

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